

Botocudo

also known as “Krén”, “Krenak”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, South American Religions

The term Botocudo is used to describe multiple unrelated societies that resisted Portuguese colonialism in present-day Brazil and retained the practice of wearing wooden ear and lip plugs (Skoggard, 2020:1). This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence that reconstructs the life of the Naknenuk subtribe of the Krén, a Botocudo group inhabiting the upper Rio Mucuri around 1884 (Nimuendajú, 1946:97). Krén religion is characterized by a belief in multiple (up to six) souls, one of which resides in the body and dies alongside it, and the presence of a host of supernatural beings known as tokón or marét that dwell in the sky. The marét have a chief, who functions essentially as a supreme high god. Shamans (who are often also chiefs) have the ability to communicate with the marét, and through them the supreme high god, and do so frequently as part of medicinal practices (Skoggard, 2020:3). For the Krén Botocudo, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1869 CE - 1894 CE

Region: Naknenuk subtribe, ca. 1884

Region tags: South America, Brazil

Naknenuk subtribe, Brazil, ca. 1884

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. *Ethnographic Atlas*. *Ethnology* 1-10.
- Source 3: Murdock, George P., and Suzanne F. Wilson. 1972. "Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-cultural codes 3." *Ethnology* 11, no. 3: 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sn02-005>
- Source 1 Description: Nimuendajú, Curt. 1946. "Social Organization and Beliefs of the Botocudo of Eastern

Brazil." *Southwestern Journal of Anthropology* Vol. 2 (1): 93-115.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sn02-000>

– Source 2 Description: Skoggard, Ian A. 2020. "Culture Summary: Botocudo." New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Botocudo are in contact with the Portuguese, who practice Catholicism. See Skoggard, 2020:1 for more information.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), internal warfare among the Botocudo is rated 4.25, which is between "Internal warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season (original code 4)" and "Internal warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year (original code 5)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: "As stated above, all Botocudo headmen were yikégn [religious specialist]; but not all yikégn were headmen" (Nimuendajú, 1946:103).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Population data is only available for dates significantly outside of the time focus or for all Botocudo (not just the Naknenuk subtribe, the focus of this entry).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In addition to the ability of communing with the marét [non-human supernatural beings], yikégn persons [religious specialists] have the power suddenly to transform themselves and others" (Nimuendajú, 1946:103).

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "In addition to the ability of communing with the marét [non-human supernatural beings], yikégn persons [religious specialists] have the power suddenly to transform themselves and others" (Nimuendajú, 1946:103).

Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that powers are obtained through encounters with marét (non-human supernatural beings). See Nimuendajú, 1946:103 for more information.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972:259, 272; note: equivalent to SCCS Variable 66).

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: "The statues represent marét [non-human supernatural beings]; they indicate the site within the village where the marét descend from the sky in order to listen to the prayer of their protégé when he sings to them" (Nimuendajú, 1946:105).

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: "The statues represent marét [non-human supernatural beings]; they indicate the site within the village where the marét descend from the sky in order to listen to the prayer of their protégé when he sings to them" (Nimuendajú, 1946:105).

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: "At the top the post terminates in a human image about one meter in height, which is carved in such fashion that the smooth, cylindrical body is formed of the red heartwood, while the head, as well as the arm and leg stumps, are of the white sapwood. The face, uniformly turned eastward, is painted with red lines in urucú" (Nimuendajú, 1946:104).

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: "At the top the post terminates in a human image about one meter in height, which is carved in such fashion that the smooth, cylindrical body is formed of the red heartwood, while the head, as well as the arm and leg stumps, are of the white sapwood. The face, uniformly turned eastward, is painted with red lines in urucú" (Nimuendajú, 1946:104).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "The other nakandyúñ [souls, those not residing in the body and thus did not die with the body] of a dead person accompany the corpse to the grave and soar above it weeping and invisible" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

– No

Notes: "Before the body's death the nakandyúñ [referring to the soul that lives within the body] dies within it" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the surviving souls] no longer eat anything and would ultimately die if the marét [non-human supernatural beings] did not take pity on them and carry them to the land Nak-ĩrám, White Country, in the sky" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the surviving souls] no longer eat anything and would ultimately die if the marét [non-human supernatural beings] did not take pity on them and carry them to the land Nak-ĩrám, White Country, in the sky" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the surviving souls] no longer eat anything and would ultimately die if the marét [non-human supernatural beings] did not take pity on them and carry them to the land Nak-ĩrám, White Country, in the sky" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that adherents' corpses are buried: "The other nakandyúñ [souls] of a dead person accompany the corpse to the grave and soar above it weeping and invisible" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that adherents' corpses are buried: "The other nakandyúñ [souls] of a dead person accompany the corpse to the grave and soar above it weeping and invisible" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "The corpse is buried in an extended position" (Skoggard, 2020:3).

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of previously human spirits and non-human supernatural beings. See questions below for details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "The marét [non-human supernatural beings] have a chief, the oldest of them all, whom Mbogmám [an informant] called Yekán kren-yirúgn (Father White-Head), while Hąnát [an informant] designated him as Borúñ kren-yirugn (White-headed Indian) or Borúñ yipakyúe (the Great Indian)" (Nimuendajú, 1946:105).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "He lives in the sky, but somewhat apart from the marét [non-human supernatural beings that also live in the sky]" (Nimuendajú, 1946:105).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekán kren-yirúgn takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekán kren-yirúgn takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Yekán kren-yirúgn owns many tame beasts (dupréñ); when they bathe in the sky, they splash the water, so that rain falls on the earth" (Nimuendajú, 1946:105).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "He sends rain and storms, but is kind to the [Botocudo] and angry when they are maltreated" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "He sends rain and storms, but is kind to the [Botocudo] and angry when they are maltreated" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "Raulino [an informant], however, declared that formerly some people had had direct communion with him" (Nimuendajú, 1946:105).

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: "If someone is ill, the people call a yikégn man [religious specialist], who sings in the afternoon (the proper time for intercourse with the marét [non-human supernatural beings]), and the spirits listen. They go to their chief, Yekân kren-yirúgn and beg him for medicines to give to their protégé, who then applies them to the patient" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through other supernatural beings

Notes: "If someone is ill, the people call a yikégn man [religious specialist], who sings in the afternoon (the proper time for intercourse with the marét [non-human supernatural beings]), and the spirits listen. They go to their chief, Yekân kren-yirúgn and beg him for medicines to give to their protégé, who then applies them to the patient" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "From the bones of the corpse the nandyóñ (ghost, spook) forms . . ." (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Nevertheless it happens occasionally that the nandyóñ appear to the living. Unless the person who sees the apparition courageously kills or at least vigorously thrashes it, his death might result" (Nimuendajú, 1946:107).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "In the sky there dwells a numerous race of spirits invisible to common mortals, who call them tokón [also called marét]" (Nimuendajú, 1946:101).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "At one time in the past the [Botocudo] did not have to work at all; marét gave them everything they needed" (Nimuendajú, 1946:101).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The marét are kind and helpful toward mankind, never growing angry" (Nimuendajú, 1946:101).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: "The marét are kind and helpful toward mankind, never growing angry" (Nimuendajú, 1946:101).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Anthropomorphic

Notes: "The marét are credited by Hąnát [an informant] with ordinary [Botocudo] size and shape; but according to Raulino [an informant] they are shorter by a head" (Nimuendajú, 1946:101).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that supernatural monitoring is present and that the supreme high god metes out punishment: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "If anyone has committed murder, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] takes away his soul and keeps it captive in the sky. The culprit's body lives on below, but grows sick and feeble" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: "It was he [the supreme high god] that instituted the use of labrets and ear-plugs . . ." (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of small-scale rituals surrounding medical practices, but not that these rituals are required: "If someone is ill, the people call a yikégn man [religious specialist], who sings in the afternoon (the proper time for intercourse with the marét [non-human supernatural beings]), and the spirits listen. They go to their chief, Yekân kren-yirúgn [the supreme high god] and beg him for medicines to give to their protégé, who then applies them to the patient" (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple extra-ritual in-group markers, including ornamentation, body painting, and lip and ear piercing. See questions below for details.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "Men wore feather ornaments and women, necklaces, bracelets and anklets" (Skoggard, 2020:3).

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Body painting

Notes: "Bodies were painted for feasts and war" (Skoggard, 2020:3).

– Yes [specify]: Lip and ear piercing

Notes: "It was he [the supreme high god] that instituted the use of labrets [in lips] and ear-plugs ..." (Nimuendajú, 1946:106).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Botocudo do not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Botocudo have bilateral descent without kindreds. Additionally, the Botocudo live in exogamous communities without localized clans or lineal kin groups (Murdock, 1962-1971, columns 19, 20, 22). Information on jurisdictional hierarchy and kin ties indicates that the Botocudo are most accurately characterized as a band.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, the Botocudo do not utilize food storage (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, the Botocudo do not utilize food storage (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, police functions among the Botocudo are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, the Botocudo do not possess a distinct written language (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Botocudo depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) providing a secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

Notes: The Botocudo depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) providing a secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).